

Implications of finite computational resources on philosophical idea that we may live in an “endless-simulation”

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Abstract. The philosophical idea that we may live in an endless simulation, where given world spawns other sub-worlds which are capable of simulating whole parent world completely from first principles, is very popular among popular culture. However it is rarely justified in the perspective, that initial computer/world has only limited amount of resources which must be somehow divided between other sub-computers in lower simulation recursive levels. In this paper I try to inject some limitations of such view and pragmatic approach to this idea.

Implications on maximum amount of simulation recursion levels

Consider such model, where initial computer has S_0 bits of memory in it’s RAM. When “simulation program” of current computer reaches required complexity to spawn other simulating sub-computers, then it spawns a pair of them, which individually can only use $S_i = S_{i-1}/2$ amount of memory bits in parent, assuming that individual computers has isolated, non-shared memory model (i is recursion level). This idea can be generalized :

It can be seen that simulating computer at i -th recursion level can have own memory size in bits

$$S_i = \frac{S_0}{2^{i-1}}$$

where S_0 is memory capacity in bits of initial starting computer. Assuming that our universe has entropy on the order $S_0 = 10^{120}$ bits and that the last recursion level computers will have only 1 bit of memory in their disposal, due to the nature of divide-and-conquer algorithm, one can calculate how many levels of recursion such system may perform :

$$i_{max} = 1 + \log_2 S_0$$

. Which gives about ≈ 400 levels of simulating recursion. This is a very far from calling such process an “endless-simulation”, cause in an endless recursion i_{max} should approach infinity.

Implications on computational complexity

Lets assume that a computer in any simulation level needs to perform N steps for completing a full simulation cycle. Also it's natural to expect that each child-computer is borrowing computational power from a parent computer. This boils-down that such recursively-simulating initial machine will have computational complexity of :

$$\mathcal{O}(2^{i-1}N^i)$$

. Given that we deduced that in such initial machine there can be maximum of 400 simulation levels, one can express computational complexity of such simulating initial machine :

$$\mathcal{O}(2^{399}N^{400})$$

. Obviously that this is a super-slow operation and almost expected that such initial simulating machine would crash or hang at some point or another.

Conclusions. Given universe entropy, maximum number of simulation recursions (400) was calculated- which is clearly far from an endless-simulation stereotype in a popular culture. Also it was found that simulation algorithm computational complexity $\mathcal{O}(2^{399}N^{400})$ is too high for expecting it to be feasible. Thus it's unnatural to expect that such universe simulating algorithm can be borned either on natural or artificial bases. It also means that most probably we don't live in an endless-simulation world or be alone in simulation algorithm, because such algorithm would crash initial computer.